

Some Factors Related to Constraints and Stress Levels of Farmers

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Abstract

This is pilot Study. The studies were conducted in Akola district of Maharashtra state to assess the constraints and stress level of the farmers. The survey was based on the 171 farmers from 96 villages. The operational area of the research activity covered the Akola district of Vidarbha region of Maharashtra state. The present study was conducted in 96 villages of Akola district. The villages as well as the farmers were selected randomly. On having completed the data sheets through one to one interviews of the respondent farmers, it was subjected to processing to get categorical details on number of farmers under various categories. The farmers were further grouped on the basis of land holdings, soil types, yearly income levels, allied activities to support the financial needs of the family. Efforts were also made to find out the number of farmers under varying levels of indebtedness, constraints involving of personal, social and the technological nature. The awareness of the farmers regarding the government schemes, facilities like Subsidies, crop loans, crop insurances and their utilization were also taken into account.

The results revealed that almost all the farmers were exposed to the varying degrees of the constraints as well as stress levels. Among the various constraints Natural and Economic Constraints were of

major concern. The improvement in infrastructural facilities mainly the market, communication, roads storage and the timely availability of credit through government agencies are some of the factors which would give a definite relief to the farmers from the constraints and stress levels to maximum extent.

Keywords: Farmers, constraints, stress, age, family members, income, landholding, tools and implements, information sources, help taken from Government, facilities, etc.

Introduction

Agriculture has always been celebrated as the primary sector in India. India is an agrarian economy, which means, agriculture is the pre-dominant sector of the Indian economy. True to this, even today, in spite of the Indian economy opening out to the world and globalization, close to 70% of the population still depends on agriculture for its livelihood. Despite a steady decline in its share to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) agriculture remains the largest economic sector in the country. The very nature of farming itself is the cause of many strains for farming families. Farming is an isolating profession, as farmers traditionally work long hours, outside, often in bad weather and alone. An individual whose primary job functions involve livestock and agriculture is called as a farmer.

A farmer takes all the necessary steps to insure proper nourishment of the items that he raises and then sells the items to purchasers. Some farmers are able to capitalize on the need for high demand products that they produce such as organic vegetable and livestock. An NFU (National Farmer Union) survey in 1999 showed that 62% of farmers were working for more than 61 hours a week. India is an agrarian country with 60% of its population depending directly or indirectly upon agriculture. The success of agriculture in India is often attributed as gambling with monsoons because of its almost exclusive dependency on precipitation from monsoons. The failure of these monsoons can lead to a series of drought, crop failures, lack of better prices, and exploitation of the farmers by middlemen, all of which have led to a series of suicides committed by farmers across India.

A state of stress exists when unusual or excessive demands threaten a person's well-being or integrity. Extraordinary efforts are needed to master the situation and there is the danger that coping capacities will be overwhelmed with the consequence of disturbed functioning ,pain or anxiety, illness or even death. Stress defined neither by the person (coping resources ego strength etc.) nor by his reactions. (Stress responses, but rather by the inter play of the three)

Stress can originate in physiological, psychological and social condition and threaten the integrity of body personality or the social system. Threat can disturb psychological well-being and psychological functioning. Social institutions produce psychological stress. One important but often

overlooked hazard is the stress faced by many farmers and their families. While farm stress emanates from several sources, most witness saw unstable and adverse economic conditions as the most significant one in relation to farmer's health and safety. When adverse economic condition alone and in combination with other sources of stress such as fluctuating weather, long work hours, lack of information and isolation are linked to symptoms of mental and physical ill-health. Sign of mental ill-health include depression, inability to concentrate, difficulty in making decisions, sleep disturbances, increased alcohol use, reduced productivity and frequent arguments with family and friends, and one time to take suicide.

Coping with stress in farming

No matter how stressed farmers feel, they can't just call in sick. 'Practically, even if you are in the worst state of stress and shock, you still have to go outside every day, feed the sheep, milk the cows and tend to the animals,' says Brian Warren, a dairy farmer in Devon and a representative of the Farm Crisis Network which helps farming families who are experiencing problems. This culture of just getting on with things can mean that stress goes ignored. And it is not just the farmers themselves who take the brunt of the strain, but also wives and family members.

According to Caroline Davies of the RSIN who often says, it is the women who make the first move to deal with the situation. 'With the men, the initial problem is getting them to speak. It is women who will pick up the phone and talk when they are under stresses. Many calls to the RSIN come from women worried about their husbands or partners, who just won't talk about things, she adds.

Talking to someone is always the first important move towards coping, the Samaritans advice. 'The burden of uncertainty and distress caused by another setback can be overwhelming. Talking to someone can be the first step forward,' says a spokesperson. There are several organisations dedicated to helping farmers to cope with stress and providing stress counseling. Two of those organisations, the Farm Crisis Network and the Royal Agricultural Benevolent Institution, suggest the tips to help farmers cope.

“Often, when we talk about sustainable agriculture, it is sustainable in terms of products and economics not in terms of people”. We would like to see attention given to the sustainability of the people in the agricultural community. The large number of the population of the developing countries comprises small farmers and landless labours. For these farmers who are tied to subsistence levels of living considering their small size of the holding, monoculture cannot increase their income through crop development alone. Many small farmers are exposed to lots of constraints.

Some constraints are as follows.

- Lack of electricity and water for irrigation.
- Lack of knowledge about improved farm techniques.
- Lack of labour for performing farm operations.
- Uncertainty in farm income due to weather hazards.
- Low price returns from farm produce.
- Inadequate and untimely availability of crop loans.
- Insufficient capital availability.

The most important but not least is debts. In which the farmer takes the birth in debts and dies in the same condition.

Unstable and adverse economic conditions with the agricultural industry are not new. For a number of years, in Vidarbha region small farmers have experienced high level of stress arising from a number of sources, including high input cost, low market return, uncertain markets and unfavorable weather conditions. These factors have had an impact on income, debt and asset values in the industry. Farmers perceived debt, addiction, environmental problems; poor prices for farm produce, stress and family responsibilities, Government apathy, and increased cost of cultivations are private money lenders, use of chemical fertilizers and crop failure as the reasons for farmers are suicides.

For last few years every other day we read the news of farmers committing suicides. The number of farmers who have committed suicides since 1997 has crossed one lack. In this context the actual problem being faced are to be understood and analyzed. Innovative remedies have to be thought of which are to be implemented with sincerity by the Government and the implementing agencies, along with putting in place ways to rehabilitate the affected farmers. Central and State Government have announced the relief packages to the suicides affected families in Maharashtra. NABARD is the implementing agency of the package provided by Central Government. In the budget of 2008-2009, Honorable Minister for Finance has also announced massive write off to the tune of Rs. 60000 cores of the outstanding loan of small and marginal farmers and OTS for other farmers.

In India 1551 number is only to farmers for 24 x 7, in this many agricultural scientists are available for solving farmers' problems.

Objectives

- 1) To find out the various factors related to Constraints of farmers.
- 2) To find out the various factors related to stress level of farmers.
- 3) To find out co-relation of various factors with constraints and stress level of farmers.

Methodology

- Locale of the study-The study was conducted in the Akola District. 96 villages were selected for data collection in Akola District.
- Research design: An Exploratory Research methods and survey method was used.
- Sample and sampling: Representative samples of 171 farmers from many villages in Akola district were selected.
- Sampling Procedure: Questionnaires' and interview methods were used to collect samples.

Variables

(A) Independents variables

- 1) Age
- 2) Gender
- 3) Education
- 4) Family members
- 5) Family economic condition
- 6) Type of land and area of land

(A) Dependent variables

- 1) Constraints of farmers
- 2) Stress level of farmers

Tool for data collection

- 1) Preliminary information was taken with the help of Questionnaires.
- 2) Stress level in farmers was measured with “stress scale tests” by Dr. M Singh.

Results and Discussion

1) Correlation of Education with selected parameters

Sr.no	Particulars	Correlation of –Coefficient(r ²)
1	Age	-0.34943**
2	Family memders	-0.15717*
3	Income	0.166723*
4	Land holding(area)	0.185711*
5	Personal constraints	0.224472**

* Significant at 5 % level of significant

** Significant at 1% level of significant

The data presented in table no. 1 indicated that the education was positively correlated with family income, landholding and the personal constraints of farmers. While, it was negatively co-related with the age of farmer and number of members in a family.

This means with the increasing land holding of family as well as its income there was increasing in educational status of the farmers. The increasing in education was found to be associated with increased personal constraints of farmers. It was also observed that the old age farmers lacked in formal education and there was increased in education status of the farmers as their Adulthood similarly with the increasing in number of family members there was reduction in educational status of farmers.

2) *Correlated of Income with selected parameters*

Sr.no.	Particulars	Correlation of Coefficient(r2)
1	Family members	0.226088*
2	Landholding	0.55945**

* Significant at 5% level of significant

** Significant at 1% level of significant

In the case of correlation of income with family members and landholdings it was observed that in both case there was positive correlation. Indicating increase in family income, with number of members, in family and the landholding of farmers.

3) *Correlated of Area with selected parameters*

Sr.no.	Particulars	Correlation of Coefficient(r2)
1	Family members	0.434124**
2	Tools and implements	0.133291*
3	Personal constraints	-0.16087*
4	income	0.55945**

* Significant at 5% level of significant

** Significant at 1% level of significant

As regards area it was found that area was positively correlated with family members, use of tools and implements and the family income. The farmers having more landholding had more number of family members and they were capable of using improve tools and implements and as a results there was increase in family income.

It was also observed that the personal constraints of farmers were negative correlated with area i.e. the personal constraints of farmers were limited with increasing in the area.

4) *Correlation of Debt index with selected parameters*

Sr. no.	Particulars	Correlation of Coefficient(r2)
1	Information sources	0.153526*
2	Help taken from Government	0.175132*
3	Tools and implements	0.155438*
4	Economic constraints	0.178344*
5	Natural constraints	0.163489*

* Significant at 5% level of significant

** Significant at 1% level of significant

The indebtedness of the farmers exhibited positive correlation with use of information source, help taken from Government, use of tools and implements and constraints economic as well as natural constraints.

5) *Correlated of Information sources with selected parameters*

Sr. no.	Particulars	Correlation of Coefficient(r2)
1	Help Taken from Government	0.422543**
2	Tools and implements	0.244552**
3	Facilities	0.197274*

*Significant at 5%level of significant

**Significant at 1%level of significant

Information source and help taken from Government had a positive correlation. This meant that the respondent farmers using more of information source normally avail maximum Government facilities line subsidy crop insurances against the vagaries of nature similarly the information source also had a positive correlation with the use of improved tools and implements by the farmers and Facilities for farming.

6) *Correlated of Help Taken from Government with selected parameters*

Sr. no.	Particulars	Correlation of Coefficient(r2)
1	Tools and implements	0.283138**
2	Facilities	0.19395*

*Significant at 5%level of significant

**Significant at 1%level of significant

Help taken from Government and tool and implement are use had positive correlated which strongly significant. This means respondents farmers are help taken from Governments are use tools and implements in farming. The facilities are also positive correlated with help taken from Government which use some farmers in farm.

7) *Correlation of all Constraints with selected parameters*

Sr. no.	Particulars	Correlation of Coefficient(r ²)
1	Technical Constraints	0.518201**
2	Personal Constraints	0.734405**
3	Economic Constraints	0.483805**
4	Natural Constraints	0.246412**

*Significant at 5%level of significant

**Significant at 1%level of significant

The Technical constraints are positive & strongly correlated to all constraints i.e. means Technical constraints Non availability of seeds, no, availability of fertilizers and pesticides etc., no. transfer facility, no. storage and market facility, lack of awareness of modern technology.

The Personal constraints also positive and strongly all correlated to constraints. The Personal constraints mean les education, bad habits, big family, less land, sawkar/private money lenders etc.

The Natural constraints are positively and strongly correlated to all constraints. Those are adverse weather condition, saline water belt, non-irrigation, labour problems.

The Economical constraints are also positive and strongly correlated to all constraints i.e. Economic constraints are low annual income, low quality of farm, low price at harvesting time, down market.

8) *Correlation of natural constraints with selected parameters*

Sr. no.	Particulars	Correlation of Coefficient(r ²)
1	Stress	0.169576*
2	Facilities	0.159518*

* Significant at 5% level of significant

** Significant at 1% level of significant

The natural constraints and the stress also exhibited a positive correlation. This means that the exposure of the farmers to the natural calamities normally put them under severe stress. The

natural calamities like severe droughts, excessive rains, hailstorms may lead to heavy damages on farm and can become a cause of severe stress to the farmers. And also positive correlated to facilities which naturally facilities to provided to farmers

9) *Correlation of personal constraints with selected parameters*

Sr. no.	Particulars	Correlation of Coefficient(r2)
1	Economic constraints	0.15287*

* Significant at 5% level of significant

** Significant at 1% level of significant

The Personal constraints are positively correlated to Economic constraints. The Personal constraints are less education, bad habit, less land, sawkar/private money lenders, are related to Economic. Economic constraints are which mostly depends upon the Personal constraints Economic constraints i.e. low annual income, low quality of farm, low price at harvesting time, down market.

Conclusion

Correlation studies

The correlations between Independent variables and dependent variables were worked out and the data are presented in the following table.

Correlation of coefficient

Sr. no	Correlation between	Correlation coefficient
1	Educational level and age	-0.34943**
2	Educational level and landholding	0.185711*
3	Income and family members	0.226088**
4	Income and landholding	0.55945**
5	Landholding and family members	0.434124**
6	Landholding and tool & implements	0.133291*
7	Debt and economic constraints	0.178344*
8	Debt and natural constraints	0.163489*
9	Information source and help taken from Government	0.422543**
10	Information source and tools & implements use	0.244552**
11	Government help and tools & implements are use	0.283138**
12	Natural constraints and stress	0.169576*

* Significant at 5% level of significant

** Significant at 1% level of significant

The data on correlation between various parameters are presented in the table. Described following observations.

The educational level and the age group of respondent farmers exhibited a negative correlation. This showed that the educational level of the respondent farmers was found to be who as age group of the respondents farmers increased; indicating there by the younger respondent farmers had higher level of education.

Then educational level had a positive correlation with land holding there by indicating that respondent farmers having more land holding had higher level of education. This might be due to good financial support for educational activity.

Income and number of family member exhibited positive correlation. A farmer family having more number of members had higher income. This might be due to correlation of family member in carrying only farm operations there by lowering their dependence on hired labours, which ultimately results in to family savings in cost of cultivation of crops.

Income and landholding showed a positive correlation. This indicated that family income increased with the size of the land holding bigger holding had higher income composed to the small farmers.

Landholding and the family members had positive correlation. Among the respondent farmers it was observed that the number of family members are increased with the increase are in land holding had more members in the family.

The correlation between land holding and the use of tool and implements was found to be positive. This showed that the big land holders afforded to have the improved tools and implements for the carrying on the farm operation.

The debt and the economic constraints had the positive correlation. This showed that the farmers facing the economic constraints are complied to opt for debt to meet the financial crises

The debt and natural constraints also had a positive correlation. The natural constraints such on aberrant weather condition such as excessive rains/droughts during crop season sometimes lead to severe crop losses or even total crop failures. This puts the farmers in a severe financial crisis and as such they are trapped in debt.

Information source and help taken from Government had a positive correlation. This meant that the respondent farmers using more of information source normally avail maximum Government facilities line subsidy crop insurances against the vagaries of nature similarly the

information source also had a positive correlation with the use of improved tools and implements by the farmers.

The Governments help was positively correlated with the use of improved tools and implements by the respondent farmers. The Government helps in the form of subsidies induce the farmers to go for the adoption improved tools and implements for the crop cultivation.

The natural constraints and the stress also exhibited a positive correlation. This means that the exposure of the farmers to the natural calamities normally put them under severe stress. The natural calamities like severe droughts, excessive rains, hailstorms may lead to heavy damages on farm and can become a cause of severe stress to the farmers.

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